

D1.6: General Architecture description in relation to the EOSC services

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Abstract

The ExPaNDS project aims at deploying into EOSC data catalogues and data analysis services. This document describes the proposed architecture for these services and how they are planned to be integrated into EOSC.

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Acronym/Abbreviation	Definition
AAI	Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure
AARC	Authentication and Authorization for Research and Collaboration
API	Application Programming Interface
AuthN	Authentication
CI/CD	Continuous Integration/Continuous Delivery
CLI	Command Line Interface
CPU	Central Processing Unit
DC	Dublin Core
DESY	Deutsches Elektronen-Synchrotron
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EPOT	EOSC Portal Onboarding Team
ESFRI	European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures
ESS	European Spallation Source
ExPaNDS	European Open Science Cloud Photon and Neutron Data Service
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
FedCloud	Federated Cloud
FTS	File Transfer Service
GA	Grant Agreement
GP-GPU	General-Purpose Graphics Processing Unit
HPC	High Performance Computing
HTC	High Throughput Computing
HTTP	Hypertext Transfer Protocol
HZDR	Helmholtz-Zentrum Dresden-Rossendorf
IaaS	Infrastructure as a Service
ICT	Information Communication Technology
IdP	Identity Provider
IT	Information Technology
MDS	MetaData Service
MMS	Membership Management Service
NRI	National Research Infrastructure

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OAI-PMH	Open Archives Initiative – Protocol for Metadata Harvesting
OIDC	OpenID Connect
OpenAIRE	Open Access Infrastructure for Research in Europe
ORCID	Open Researcher and Contributor ID
PAN	Photon and Neutron
PaNET	Photon and Neutron Experimental Techniques
PaNOSC	The Photon and Neutron Open Science Cloud
PID	Persistent Identifier
RDA	Research Data Alliance
REST	REpresentational State Transfer
RI	Research Infrastructure
SAML	Security Assertion Markup Language
SLURM	Simple Linux Utility for Resource Management
SSO	Single Sign On
UI	User Interface
UKRI	UK Research and Innovation
VISA	Virtual Infrastructure for Scientific Analysis
VM	Virtual Machine

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Executive Summary

This deliverable describes the architecture of the ExPaNDS services, focusing on the technical aspects. It is composed of contributions by the technical work packages on catalogues and analysis as well as from EGI, our European infrastructure partner.

The document enumerates a selection of core services required to maintain the PaN overall system, essentially AAI, accounting and monitoring, as well as scientific services provided by the particular ExPaNDS PaN facilities. Particularly, software catalogues are an important prerequisite of our analysis pipelines. They are already provided by the scientific communities¹ and therefore not further described in this document. The first part of the document elaborates on how to abstract the data and analysis services with common APIs in order to make them available to portals and processing pipelines without knowing where the actual facility data, analysis stacks and ICT infrastructure resides. Agreed interfaces, e.g. APIs not only allow to abstract and federate underlying services, but they enable to run a variety of portals for different target users, like the shared PaN portal and the EOSC portal as a minimum. Moreover, as this is one of ExPaNDS high level objectives, the document describes the relationship between services provided by ExPaNDS RIs and the EOSC as well as their interdependencies. The architecture described in this report is finally validated via PaN scenarios that walk through its components and the interactions between them.

ExPaNDS has established strong synergies with the PaNOSC ESFRI cluster project² with which we naturally share a large number of objectives.

This deliverable focuses on high level architecture services. Deployment of ExPaNDS services at the different facilities and availability from EOSC are presented in separate deliverables, see D3.3³ Demonstrate ICAT and SciCat released with APIs compatible to ExPaNDS federated EOSC services and D4.4⁴ Analysis Services.

1 <https://software.pan-data.eu/>

2 PaNOSC project website: <https://www.panosc.eu/>

3 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6363591>

4 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6305000>

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1. Introduction

Besides improving the establishment of FAIR principles in data, metadata and analysis pipelines of national PaN facilities, the major technical aspect of ExPaNDS is to unify the access to core and scientific ICT resources for PaN communities and ideally for associated or interested non PaN scientists.

During the start of the project steps to move forwards were identified in particular where synergies with other projects, initiatives and the knowledge of already available, well-established services could get us ahead within the scope of our funding.

Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure (AAI) provides an example of such a synergy. As almost all distributed scientific endeavours require such an infrastructure, considerable effort has been invested to verify both the tools and the legal and technical guidelines to build an AAI infrastructure compatible with European and national laws, which supports research in many scientific research domains and provides a common AAI fabric through which different services may be integrated.

Similarly important, if not essential, is the alignment of ExPaNDS activities with the PaNOSC project as outlined in our Grant Agreement (GA). PaNOSC is targeting almost identical objectives for those facilities, being members of the ESFRI group in the PaN domain. Specifically, and further detailed in the remain of this document, ExPaNDS pillars for the unification and standardisation of distributed scientific computing are as follows:

- Access to data, covering the provisioning of common standards in accessing the data itself as well as its metadata catalogues.
- Access to analysis and processing pipelines, easily portable between facilities as well as support for traditional access to monolithic pipelines through remote desktops to batch facilities operated on standard or HPC hardware.
- Access to the actual computing infrastructures which could be traditional batch systems, including HPC clusters, like SLURM, but increasingly modern Cloud Management Frameworks, like OpenStack, container based systems, like Kubernetes or even server-less systems, like OpenWhisk.
- Access to training, e-learning and documentation resources via a training portal

EXPANDS chose to implement the overall architecture in stages, starting by commonly agreed APIs that are now facilitating and fostering the use of PaN infrastructures allowing scientists to focus on their science instead of having to deal with data transfers and storage issues and making access to computing and data more efficient and FAIR.

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2. Description of the ExPaNDS architecture

The ExPaNDS architecture is designed to allow seamless connection to catalogue and analysis services hosted either at participant facilities or elsewhere through front-end portals, thereby allowing transparent access to services for users. Essential elements of this are:

- A catalogue of available data sets and their location.
- A catalogue of data services available at host institutions.
- A catalogue of training and documentation resources.
- Correlation of which datasets and analysis services are available together.

In designing the architecture, the following properties have been identified but may not be universally available at all host institutions depending on local configuration and policies:

- Single Sign-On (SSO) authentication;
- Matching of datasets to compatible or suggested analysis services (depends on this metadata being available and searchable);
- Display only data and/or services available to a particular user (not all services or data are available everywhere so display only those which the user can use).

The following Figure 1 represents the proposed architecture to achieve the above goals for the ExPaNDS project.

Fig. 1: ExPaNDS architecture - overview

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This architecture proposes integrating services and APIs to the existing infrastructures, taking advantage of the commonalities detected on one side, and pursuing synergies and economy of scale on the other.

The ExPaNDS architecture is composed of independent modules, commonly referred to as microservices, linked by APIs to enable maximum flexibility:

- **PaN Portal:** where the PaN users connect to search data and request for analysis services. Alternatively, CLI access or command line interfaces to well defined APIs provide also access to the services;
- **PaN Metadata Services:** Also referred to as Metadata Catalogue services provide search services for locating data sets;
- **PaN Compute Services:** Data analysis services based on cloud or remote desktops;
- **AAI:** Authentication and Authorization Services.

2.1. PaN Portal

Fig. 2: ExPaNDS architecture - PaN Portal

At the beginning of the ExPaNDS project, it was envisioned that the architecture would be implemented in a top-down manner, first installing a commonly agreed web portal initiated and provided by the PaNOSC project and then linking it to the different facility ICT infrastructures through their specific implementations of the common PaN metadata catalogue and data analysis services APIs.

Since then, a change of strategy has been decided in order to allow for more flexibility and to give each facility the capability to adapt its architecture implementation timeline to its specific infrastructure configuration constraints.

ExPaNDS architecture is now built on top of the common APIs, allowing the opportunity for each facility to connect them, in a first step, to portals of choice that best suit its current infrastructure. The final goal still remains however to be the use of a common portal accessible from the EOSC marketplace. The results already obtained show that this strategy is already a success.

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As sketched in Figure 2, the architecture is built on top of three pillars representing the three core services APIs: PaN Compute Services, PaN Metadata Services, PaN Data Services. As described in Section 2.2, the purpose of PaN Data Services is to provide the PaN community end-users with means to access and filter PaN data coming from different facilities. This is realised through the PaN Search API that targets the catalogue services to get back the metadata that best answers user requests from the PaN portal.

The PaN MetaData Catalogues are the data management services deployed locally at each facility providing the user with:

- The landing pages associated with the DOIs that come out as results of the PaN Search API requests from the portal.
- The UI for browsing the local MetaData database and getting access to the related datasets.
- The endpoint for metadata harvesting.

Metadata Catalogues follow the recommendations described in the PaN Metadata Framework for FAIR implementation first introduced in D2.2 Draft recommendations for FAIR Photon and Neutron Data Management⁵. The framework presents a summary of all metadata involved in the PaN data lifecycle and prioritises them according to the RDA FAIR Data Maturity Model⁶.

Details regarding the PaN Compute Services, third architecture pillar, are given in Section 2.3. covering PaN Data Analysis Compute Services. When an end user searches and finds data sets relevant to his research field of interest, he may just want to download them to his laptop or local laboratory data storage system and process them with the compute resources available to him.

Such a way of operating is already becoming and will be increasingly unmanageable for small laboratories. The data deluge we are going towards, due to the exponential performance growth of instrument and data acquisition environment setups provided by facilities to the scientific community, is leading to ever higher throughput data rates. The need for user's provision with seamless access to remote compute resources near the location of data to be analysed is becoming mandatory.

The PaN Compute Services also referred to as Cloud and Remote Desktop services are the link given by the PaN portal to the web interfaces through which the user can launch the Data Analysis software needed to process the data sets found via the PaN Search API without having to go through the cumbersome tasks of software installation or compute resources provisioning.

5 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4312825>

6 <https://doi.org/10.15497/rda00050>

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2.2. PaN Data and Metadata Catalogue Services (Search) ⁷

In the PaN and EOSC communities, end-users often need to access and filter data coming from different facilities. A high volume of data helps the communities to run further analyses and progress in scientific development.

In the course of the project, two major use cases have been identified, one helping the Photon and Neutron community in the FAIR journey, later referred to as the *PaN search service*, and the second enabling the integration of PaN facilities with the EOSC community and thus facilitating its members, namely the *integration with EOSC services*. The two differ because different communities need different searching tools, thus the former provides a specific and in-depth search interface for PaN users, and the latter a more generic cross-domain search functionality as its purpose is to serve a more heterogeneous community.

A prerequisite set by both use cases is for a PaN facility to have a *data catalogue*, such as ICAT or SciCat (later referred to as *data catalogue service* and *data repository*), in place. One of the roles of ExPaNDS is to accompany PaN facilities in the *data catalogue* adoption.

In the two following subsections, we describe such use cases and present the corresponding PaN data catalogue service architecture.

2.2.1 The PaN search service architecture

In the PaN community, end-users often need to access and filter PaN data coming from different facilities. Therefore, The PaN federated search service is designed as a RESTful service to forward the end-user's query to the data catalogue of each facility and to serve as a hub for collecting PaN data from facilities.

In what follows, it is stressed the difference between an API and a service, where the former represents an interface definition, or requirement, and the latter an implementation according to its API definition. The API definition is of central importance because it specifies what flows between communication layers, while the service implements, in addition to other things, how such information is massaged to comply with its API definition.

There are three components involved:

- The PaN search-API, which sets the APIs requirements for the search interface to the data catalogues, defining the APIs expected inputs and outputs.
- The PaN federated search service, which is a RESTful service, implements the PaN search-APIs protocol, forwarding queries and aggregating results from search API services at different facilities.
- The (ICAT, SciCat, Custom Site) PaN search services, implementing the PaN search-APIs protocol, translating the incoming request following the PaN search-API standard to one specific to the Site API and responding accordingly to the PaN search-API standard.

The three of them were designed and developed by collaborators in the PaNOSC and ExPaNDS projects. In the course of the ExPaNDS project, both ICAT and SciCat projects

⁷ Gonzalez-Beltran, Alejandra, Minotti, Carlo, Davies, Louise, Leorato, Marco, Richards, Matthew, Krahl, Rolf, Padmanabhan, Sudha, & Bozhinov, Viktor. (2022). Demonstrate ICAT and SciCat released with APIs compatible with ExPaNDS federated EOSC services (1.1). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6363591>

have developed an interface that retrieves PaN data from the data catalogues, compliant with the PaN search-API requirements, and which are then consumed by the PaN federated search service. It is noted that the ICAT and SciCat PaN interface, or PaN search service, differ from their respective data catalogues service and corresponding API, as they provide functionalities very specific to the PaN community. Figure 3 shows the architecture of the PaN search.

Fig. 3: PaN search architecture

It is to be noted that it suffices to have one search service implementation per catalogue service (e.g. ICAT, SciCat), as opposed to one per facility. In this context, ExPaNDS and PaNOSC have jointly been developing Translation services for the two main data catalogues (ICAT and SciCat) and will work on helping all facilities to adopt the proper one.

As Figure 3 shows, each facility will develop and deploy its PaN search service and link it to the PaN federated search service⁸, which is currently hosted by ESS⁹, a PaNOSC partner.

2.2.2 PaN-ontologies service

It is worth shortly deep-diving into the middle and bottom layers of figure 3. These layers can include many more services, as long as they follow the PaN search-APIs, and an example is the PaN federated search service, currently in use and mentioned in section 2.2.1.

⁸ <https://federated.scicat.ess.eu>

⁹ <https://europeanspallationsource.se>

Another such service is the pan-ontologies-API, a RESTful service that links the ontologies - currently only the PaNET ontology as defined in D3.2¹⁰ - to the search-API. At a high level, the service works by pulling and caching information from external ontology repositories, and in particular, the *GET /techniques/pan-ontology* endpoint translates the query from the user input (e.g. in the PaN portal) to a new query sent to the search service, having added the logic from the PaNET ontology. In PaNET, we want to expand the query from the user, when looking for a particular technique, to include all the techniques which descend from it, namely the techniques which are different specifications of the same input class.

Given its role in the data model, namely the fact that it does not depend on the data catalogue specific implementation (e.g. ICAT and SciCat can use the same implementation), the pan-ontologies service could work either at the level of the PaN federated search service (the middle layer of figure 3), thus becoming a federated service or at the level of the data catalogue of each facility (each box named “search-API” in the bottom layer of figure 3).

2.2.3 Scoring service

Another service, now acting at the level of the bottom layer of figure 3 is the scoring service¹¹.

The user submits a query together with the number of items (results) requested to the PaN federated search service. The query and the number of items requested are relayed as-is to each connected PaN search service endpoint at all participating facilities.

Each facility retrieves the relevant results from its catalogue based on the query. The results are scored and prioritised locally. Each facility will send the full requested number of scored results back to the federated search layer. The federated search merges together all the results from all the participating facilities, sorts them according to the assigned scores and returns only the most relevant ones to the user.

A further mention to the *PaN data catalogue service architecture*, with integration, implementation and deployment examples can be found in the report around deliverable D3.3¹².

Assuming services comply with the suggested standards, the number of those endpoints is only limited by the scalability of the selected framework.

2.2.4 Integration with EOSC services

EOSC services, such as B2FIND¹³ and OpenAIRE, cover a use case very similar to the PaN search one, differing only from the target community searching for the data. These services

10 Release V1.0 ExPaNDS Ontology available as an EOSC online service:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4806026>

11 <https://github.com/panosc-eu/panosc-search-scoring>

12 Gonzalez-Beltran, Alejandra, Minotti, Carlo, Davies, Louise, Leorato, Marco, Richards, Matthew, Krahl, Rolf, Padmanabhan, Sudha, & Bozhinov, Viktor. (2022). Demonstrate ICAT and SciCat released with APIs compatible with ExPaNDS federated EOSC services (1.1).

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6363591>

13 <http://b2find.eudat.eu/>

provide an interface to data, not limited to the PaN field as their aim is to aggregate as many datasets as possible, relevant to the end-user's query. The data catalogues in ExPaNDs, as a part of their FAIR commitment, have implemented interfaces to be harvested by these EOSC services, named (ICAT, SciCat, Custom Site) OAI-PMH service in Figure 4. This interface is usually addressed as specified by the OAI-PMH protocol¹⁴ and follows the generic Dublin Core metadata guidelines¹⁵ for dataset discovery.

Figure 4 shows the EOSC services architecture.

Fig. 4: The EOSC services architecture

The EOSC services architecture consists of two major components, relying on the presence of at least one *catalogue service* and one *data repository*:

- The OAI-PMH, which sets the APIs for the search interface to the data catalogues,
- The (ICAT, SciCat, Custom Site) OAI-PMH RESTful services, implementing the OAI-PMH, translating the incoming request following the OAI-PMH standard to one specific to the Site API and responding accordingly to the OAI-PMH standard.

This architecture enables the EOSC services to harvest the OAI-PMH APIs of the PaN facilities and collect data accordingly.

In this case, B2FIND and OpenAIRE cover both the search, the aggregation and the end-user's User Interface (UI) part.

¹⁴ <https://www.openarchives.org/pmh/>

¹⁵ <https://dublincore.org>

2.3. PaN Compute Services (Data Analysis)

Fig. 4: ExPaNDS architecture - Data analysis services

The proposed Cloud Services architecture covers two different technologies: Virtual Machines and Containers.

Users select datasets to work with and open a new connection to the cloud services of the facility hosting those datasets. Depending on the type of service, interfaces provided by the PaN portal to each of the facilities redirects the user to the right implementation of the Common Compute API to deliver the underlying service. The latter can either be a remote desktop, giving access to complex applications, running in VMs within Cloud Management Frameworks (OpenStack) or, using more modern approaches, offering “Jupyter Notebooks” through e.g., containers, orchestrated by Kubernetes or similar technologies.

The architecture also covers the need to interface HPC resources required for large-scale data analysis or if particular hardware setups are needed, like access to GP-GPUs or low latency networks. The HPC resources can be operated with Cloud technologies or made available through remote desktop access as already mentioned in the section above. In the second case the remote desktop service gives access to a “Slurm workload manager” based job control system operating the HPC clusters.

Similar to search APIs, the common compute API’s are coordinated between ExPaNDS and PaNOSC.

As indicated in the deliverable D4.4 “Data Analysis Services”¹⁶, ExPaNDS partners focused their work on five representative data processing/analysis use cases to get them packaged in a way to be exchangeable between all the facilities and easily adaptable to the different local infrastructures. As described in D4.4, there is no one-to-one relationship between the

¹⁶ <https://zenodo.org/record/6305000>

five use cases and the technical implementation at the different ExPaNDS facilities. To simplify the adoption of our services and to increase the likelihood of achieving sustainable solutions, all project partners based their implementations on concepts and environments which represent state of the art open-source projects e.g. GitHub, GitLab and CI/CD or on already available core services in the EOSC Marketplace.

Different kinds of infrastructure implementations are used:

- JupyterHub service that can launch instances of JupyterLab using the local HPC cluster by submitting jobs to a Slurm cluster (e.g. ALBA)
- JupyterHub service running on top of a Kubernetes platform where the configuration is such that users can supply their own Notebook container, complete with dependencies, by providing a URL to a container hosted in any container registry (e.g. Docker Hub) (Diamond, MAXIV)
- VM-based Data Analysis as a Service platform (UKRI/ISIS)
- Use of the PanOSC VISA platform on top of Openstack (Desy, SOLEIL)
- Use of an OpenStack infrastructure to generate container instances that run pre-packaged Jupyter Notebooks. (HZDR)

To get all these different implementations harmonised to fit in the PaN Compute Services depicted in the figure above, discussions are ongoing as of Q2 2022 with the PanOSC partners in order to extend the VISA API Server¹⁷ to come out with a standard PaN Common Compute API that can be translated into:

- IaaS stack APIs e.g. OpenStack or Proxmox generating Virtual Machines or Docker containers running pre-packaged pipelines on a facility configurable Cloud Infrastructure.
- A Kubernetes API launching containerised Jupyter Notebooks on a facility configurable JupyterHub service.
- A Remote Desktop Service running on top of Slurm based HPC infrastructure.

When the analysis environments are not physically located with the data, data transfer services should be activated. These services are dealt with as part of PaNOSC WP6 e.g., see data transfer use case with EGI DataHub¹⁸.

The results of a computation or analysis services can lead to processed datasets that follow the FAIR practices ensuring that workflows and analysis services are reproducible leading to the same results.

2.4. Training infrastructure

One of the goals of ExPaNDS is to train research scientists in order to better understand the issues, methods and available computational RI infrastructures to address critical research questions. The PaN-training catalogue provides a one-stop shop for trainers and trainees to discover online information and content:

¹⁷ <https://github.com/ILLGrenoble/visa-api-server>

¹⁸ <https://www.panosc.eu/use-cases/use-case-7-data-transfer-using-egi-datahub-onedata/>

- For trainers the catalogue offers an environment for sharing materials and event information.
- For trainees, it offers a convenient gateway via which to identify relevant training events and resources, and to perform specific, guided analysis tasks via training workflows to provide FAIR research.

The following elements are available from the PaN-training catalogue:

- **Training Material and Events:** Materials in the PaN-training catalogue can be accessed at any time. These may be in a variety of different formats, including online tutorials, videos, presentations. A significant portion of the content is harvested from the e-learning platform developed in the PaNOSC project, but also from third-party sources like LEAPS and LENS.
- **Training Workflows:** Essential features in the PaN-training catalogue are the graphical training tools or Training Workflows. The main types of workflows are: Educational Resources, Learning Pathways and Experiment Maps. These encapsulate different types of, and/or approaches to, training, at different levels of granularity.
- **Content providers:** Content providers are entities (such as academic or research institutions, non-profit organisations, portals etc.) that provide training materials of relevance to the PaN community.

2.5. Authentication and Authorization infrastructure

The Authentication and Authorization infrastructure (AAI) is one of the core components of a technical architecture composed of distributed services and users. Prerequisites imposed by European and national laws, policies of our project partners, and the fact that we intend to closely collaborate with the PaNOSC ESFRI cluster as well as with other players in the EOSC, led us to the adoption and compliance with commonly accepted standards as described in the AARC blueprint document¹⁹. Another advantage of following the AARC recommendations, besides the benefit of technical standardisation, is the fact that the blueprint provides templates for the necessary legal policies to operate identity providers, services and proxies. The legal aspects of imposing cross-facility authentication are not to be underestimated, further motivating the use of an existing standard.

The migration of the UmbrellaID legacy infrastructure to the GEANT eduTEAMS²⁰ platform as described in PaNOSC deliverable D6.3 “Integration of the PaN AAI into the EOSC”²¹, provided the basis for the adoption of an AAI solution, compliant with the AARC blueprint

19 <https://aarc-project.eu/architecture/>

20 https://www.geant.org/Services/Trust_identity_and_security/Pages/eduTEAMS.aspx

21 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5913472>

and interoperable with the EOSC AAI and other Infrastructure Proxies e.g. EGI Check-In²², Indigo IAM²³ and B2ACCESS²⁴.

Scientists can authenticate to facilities via means of UmbrellaID, eduGAIN, ORCID Identity Provider (IdP) or via the facilities' local authentication services. Authenticated users can be granted or denied access based on the user's identity and the permissions assigned by the facilities. The eduTeams platform provides not only the proxy component but also the Metadata Service (MDS) that manages user's attributes and the Membership Management Service (MMS) that manages user's membership to groups.

This AAI allows establishing the necessary controls and trust framework to access services and research outputs, (e.g. datasets, publications, etc.) at the appropriate level across the PaN infrastructure. Whether resources are publicly available as open data or as protected resources at the local facilities, the PaN solution in place should enforce the right level of protection in agreement with local policies (as open as possible as close as necessary). While federated authentication AuthN provides a Single Sign On solution, federated policies, or group membership authorization across the PaN infrastructure, would enhance the access experience when shared resources across the facilities are available to the users. Federated authorization services will be explored towards the last phase of the project as authorization services evolve in the AAI solution from PaNOSC.

Users therefore, must have at least one trusted identity provider issuing OIDC (OpenID Connect) or SAML credentials in order to authenticate to the facilities. They may also require accounts to be created at the facilities, hosting data and data analysis services as a separate step. This guarantees that the service-hosting facility keeps complete control over the scientists using their services. A mapping from the UmbrellaID AAI to the local accounts when used is then necessary. In general, authorization can be based on individual credentials or group membership.

22 <https://www.egi.eu/services/check-in/>

23 <https://www.indigo-datacloud.eu/identity-and-access-management>

24 <https://sp.eudat.eu/catalog/resources/d04af0f5-2253-4ee4-8181-3a5a961ccd49>

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3. Relationship of the ExPaNDS architecture with EOSC

One of the main ExPaNDS objectives is integrating the PaN services into EOSC helping the very diverse scientific user groups to benefit from the EOSC to boost scientific outputs.

ExPaNDS enhances services from the Photon and Neutron community adopting EOSC best practices and standards facilitating the interoperability with the core and horizontal services offered via the EOSC (AAI, Helpdesk, computing and storage resources etc.) and integrating them when their adoption is considered useful and convenient (e.g. data transfer services, computing or storage facilities to scale-up, new analytics, etc.). ExPaNDS is also a contributor to the selection and the definition of EOSC standard interfaces leveraging the experiences of its community on dealing with large, distributed IT infrastructures and data sources.

ExPaNDS enriches the EOSC offer on data management services fostering the “Open Data” paradigm for the benefit of the wider EOSC community. A similarly important objective of the project is to increase the number of scientists which can rely on an efficient and interoperable European Photon and Neutron ICT infrastructure. Scientists working on several different scientific disciplines (e.g., biology, materials, chemistry, technology, nuclear physics, pharmacology, high-energy physics, cultural heritage ...) can take advantage of these facilities.

ExPaNDS provides harmonised services offered by the national RIs. National RI FAIR data is made accessible and shareable across broadening user communities ensuring RI's data catalogues conform to common EOSC standards and APIs and made available within the PaN, the EOSC Portal²⁵ and the EOSC Marketplace²⁶, B2FIND²⁷ and OpenAIRE²⁸.

3.1. ExPaNDS services for the EOSC

The ExPaNDS services for the European Photon and Neutron Community leverage the distributed architecture depicted in Section 2 and will be offered to the wider EOSC community through PaN portals and standard API's.

Although the PaN portal and its APIs are the main point of access for these services, the ExPaNDS services are published in the EOSC Portal when these are ready for consumption by the wider community providing additional entry points for usage of ExPaNDS services.

ExPaNDS follows closely the activities related to the design and evolution of the EOSC Portal to assess the best way to publish its services in the EOSC Marketplace together with

25 The EOSC Portal: <https://www.eosc-portal.eu/>

26 <https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu>

27 <http://b2find.eudat.eu>

28 <https://explore.openaire.eu>

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EOSC Regional projects from the InfraEOSC-05 Collaboration²⁹. ExPaNDS can also benefit from programmatic interfaces to automatically publish ExPaNDS services in the EOSC portals once validated against the EOSC Rules of Participation and will discuss its evolution and further requirements with the EOSC-Future³⁰.

The following picture shows the possible different access channels to the ExPaNDS services.

Fig. 5: Accessing ExPaNDS Services in EOSC. Photon and Neutron communities and other EOSC user communities will be able to access the ExPaNDS services through the PaN portal, 3rd party portals operated by PaN facilities and, possibly, via the EOSC portal.

3.2. EOSC service onboarding

ExPaNDS RI's can register services in the EOSC Portal from the dedicated EOSC Providers Portal³¹, a platform where service providers can onboard their organisations, register and manage their resources, and track the usage of the resources. Fig. 6 shows a three step-staged process to follow to register new services on the EOSC Portal.

²⁹ <https://www.eosc-pillar.eu/infraeosc-5-collaboration>

³⁰ <https://eoscfuture.eu>

³¹ <https://eosc-portal.eu/for-providers>

Fig. 6 The service onboarding process in EOSC

Step 1: The providers register him/herself into EOSC to obtain EOSC AAI credentials and login to the portal, using the Identity Provider of choice.

Step 2: Provider registration/update requires information from the organisation as defined in the Provider Profile.

Step 3: Resource (e.g., services) registration can be processed under a registered Provider according to the information defined in the Resource Profile.

The EOSC Portal Onboarding Team (EPOT) validates the provided information against the Inclusion Criteria derived from the Rules of Participation. In the case of invalid or outdated information (during and after onboarding) regarding their offerings, the providers will be notified by EPOT and proceed with improvement actions.

Providers can manage their complete resource portfolio in the EOSC Portal, through the EOSC Providers Portal. They can update the information about their organisation, resources, the ordering configurations, create draft resources, publish or unpublish resources in the Marketplace and view resources shared and co-provided with other organisations in the EOSC Portal. They can also view messages coming from users, statistics about visits and use of their offerings, as well as a complete timeline of changes and actions applied to their resource.

Resources must be onboarded by a legal entity (although the legal entity may do so on behalf of a project or consortium in which they participate, with the agreement of those groups).

Providers onboarding a resource must assert that they are able to ensure the resource is delivered by them or their collaborators and agree to remove resources which are no longer operational or available.

3.3. Map ExPaNDs architecture with EOSC architecture

EOSC has been envisaged as a key instrument to facilitate access to scientific services, lower barriers between the EOSC Core and the EOSC Exchange layers to integrate and compose services and promote the usage of services between adjacent communities. To reach this aim, the EOSC Architecture Interoperability Framework³² defines interoperability guidelines that would allow it to identify EOSC ‘compliant’ services. These services would offer well-established and documented interfaces for usage and integration, based on well-known standard or APIs, facilitating their exploitation and the combined usage of more EOSC services. An initial draft of the EOSC Architecture and Interoperability Framework was published in December 2021 by the EOSC-Future project. The draft presents the high level EOSC architecture and a governance framework with the final aim of fostering interoperability and, ultimately, service composability.

Fig 7 shows how the different PaN services and research products are made available to the EOSC Exchange. More specifically, ExPaNDs contributes to PaN thematic services such as the community driven metadata catalogues, SciCat and ICaT as data sources or PaN analytic portals (VISA portal), as well as more generic services that can be reused horizontally across the PaN community or other communities of interest (e.g. PaN ontologies or dedicated remote desktop clients that provide access to the computing environments).

Together with the horizontal services provided by the e-infrastructures, EGI, GEANT, OpenAire and EUDAT, the PaN ecosystem in EOSC becomes a vibrant set of resources that researchers and providers can reuse to deliver Open Science and value-added data and services.

The next section describes integration with EOSC Core services, which provide the operational foundation of the EOSC platform.

32 <https://eosc-portal.eu/sites/default/files/EOSC%20Future-WP3-EOSC%20Architecture%20and%20Interoperability%20Framework-2021-12-22%5B17%5D%5B6%5D-2.pdf>

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Fig.7 ExPaNDS services in EOSC

3.3.1. Integration with EOSC Core AAI

As described in Section 2.4, ExPaNDS architecture adopts an Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure (AAI) compliant with the AARC Blueprint Architecture 2019³³ and the AARC guidelines³⁴ to guarantee interoperability with other EOSC AAIs enabling Single Sign-On (SSO) access for ExPaNDS users in EOSC and granting access to ExPaNDS services to other EOSC users.

The diagram depicted in Fig. 8 shows a researcher's perspective following the AARC Blueprint Architecture. According to this architecture, ExPaNDS adopts a community AAI for the Photon and Neutron Community. To enable the access from any AARC-compliant community AAI to services and use resources of different e-Infrastructure, the PaN community AAI will be connected to different e-Infrastructure proxies (e.g.: EGI via Check-in³⁵). The mapping of Community AAI with the e-Infrastructure proxy of EGI was already implemented during the first part of the EOSC Future project. Thanks to this work, PaN users authenticated with UmbrellaID³⁶ can perform data analytics on the resources offered by EGI.

33 <https://zenodo.org/record/3672785#.XlkiT2hKg2w>

34 <https://aarc-project.eu/guidelines/>

35 <https://www.egi.eu/service/check-in/>

36 <https://umbrellaid.org/>

Fig. 8: High-level view of AAI architecture for access to EOSC resources: A researcher's perspective following the AARC Blueprint Architecture.

The AAI framework in EOSC will be further extended supporting the Federation of Communities AAI's and Infrastructure Proxies that are compliant with the AARC BluePrint Architecture. In this new AAI architecture, UmbrellaID, the PaN Community AAI, will be one of the Early Adopters that will be integrated in the EOSC AAI Federation. Thanks to this integration, members of the PaN community will be able to use their UmbrellaID Identity to discover and access resources from all the federated e-Infrastructures without having to re-register across infrastructures. The high-level architecture of the EOSC AAI Federation is depicted in Fig. 9. The design and implementation of the EOSC AAI Federation is taking place in the scope of the EOSC-Future project; operation is planned for October 2022.

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Fig.9 EOSC AAI Federation

3.3.2. EOSC helpdesk, accounting and monitoring

ExPaNDs facilities can adopt the desired level of integration with the EOSC Core service³⁷ such as **EOSC helpdesk**, accounting and monitoring tools. These services take on great importance to connect ExPaNDs with EOSC. For example, when ExPaNDs services are published in the EOSC Portal, it is necessary to offer a way to users accessing the services via this channel to interact with the service support team, this can be achieved with the EOSC helpdesk³⁸. **EOSC accounting** is another service that would allow a measurement of the uptake of the ExPaNDs services and datasets published in EOSC allowing the project to demonstrate its impact to the EC e.g., DESY and UKRI are an integral part of the EGI FedCloud federation where Cloud Compute and HPC/HTC services are accounted for, reporting on CPU hours and utilisation of the allocated resources. EOSC Future is developing an accounting service to accommodate the metrics and usage indicators from the different e-infrastructures and RIs in a consistent way integrating both services and research products. The release is expected for September 2022.

Finally, **EOSC monitoring** will be used to report in real-time the availability, reliability and status of the ExPaNDs services published in EOSC Exchange.

³⁷ D3.3a Architecture and Interoperability Guidelines for Operational Services of the EOSC Core. To be published at <https://eoscfuture.eu/library/>

³⁸ <https://eoscfuture.eu/helpdesk.eosc-portal.eu>

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EOSC helpdesk, accounting and monitoring have been conceived as distributed systems with a central catch-all instance and interfaces towards federated instances. Each provider in EOSC can choose different ways to adopt and integrate with these services (using a central instance, interconnecting its own instance with interface A or interface B, etc).

The project is following the progress done in EOSC Future for the evolution of the EOSC Core services. As the services mature and release more stable versions, ExPaNDS service providers will consider, in case of adoption, both to use the EOSC central instances or to interconnect its own instances with the EOSC central ones. ExPaNDS will adopt standard interfaces as much as possible compliant with the technical specifications of the EOSC Core services.

3.4. ExPaNDS requirements for EOSC

The ExPaNDS project formulated early on a series of requirements to be fulfilled by EOSC. These requirements were elaborated later as presented in the Positioning Papers on EOSC, Insights from Regional Projects & Infrastructures³⁹ from the InfraEOSC-05 Collaboration. A summary of the requirements and their status as of Q2 2022 are described in Table 1.

Table 1 ExPaNDS requirements for EOSC

Requirement	Status
An easy to use, possible automatic, interface to publish ExPaNDS services in the EOSC Portal.	Providers can now make use of the Portal API's to publish and update resources ⁴⁰ .
The definition of EOSC APIs and standards to facilitate the integration between services and components	EOSC has published an interoperability framework and guidelines to allow for service composability among EOSC Exchange services as well as integration with EOSC Core. Services like accounting, ordering, onboarding already offer standard API's for integration.
The adoption of AAI systems compliant with the AARC Blueprint Architecture and its guidelines.	The EOSC AAI federation is expected to be operational by Q4 2022, allowing PaN Community AAI to interact with resources from other communities of the EOSC federation.
A central helpdesk to collect user requests from the EOSC Portal with interfaces to connect external helpdesks.	EOSC central helpdesk already allows for registration of user queries via a ticketing system. Further developments will allow integration with existing infrastructure helpdesk systems.

³⁹ <https://zenodo.org/record/3831561#.YmhPSy8w3T8>

⁴⁰ <https://providers.eosc-portal.eu/openapi>

<p>A central tool for accounting the usage of resources with interfaces to connect external accounting systems</p>	<p>A Proof of Concept (PoC) has been developed⁴¹ where a model for metrics definition across infrastructures has been defined for both services and research products: Services accounting: Release Q3 2022. Research Products accounting: Release Q2 2022, provided by OpenAIRE UsageCounts service.</p>
<p>A central tool for monitoring services with interfaces to connect external monitoring systems</p>	<p>A monitoring service based on ARGO⁴² is available to monitor EOSC Core⁴³ and EOSC Exchange⁴⁴ services at several levels of integration.</p>
<p>Availability of data transfer services</p>	<p>EOSC Marketplace offers Data Transfer services, e.g. EGI FTS Data Transfer⁴⁵.</p>
<p>EOSC computing and storage services to scale-up when needed</p>	<p>Computing and Storage services are available from EOSC Marketplace, e.g. EGI Cloud Compute⁴⁶ and EGI Online Storage⁴⁷.</p>

41 <https://acc.devel.argo.grnet.gr>

42 <https://argoeu.github.io/argo-monitoring/>

43 <https://eosccore.ui.argo.grnet.gr>

44 <https://argo.eosc-portal.eu>

45 <https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/services/egi-data-transfer>

46 <https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/services/egi-cloud-compute>

47 <https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/services/egi-online-storage>

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4. PaN scenarios for architecture validation

In this section, we validate the ExPaNDS architecture by selecting three scenarios. These scenarios have been chosen to cover the elements of the architecture. This section is not intended to provide an exhaustive list of scenarios. The validation is achieved by walking through these scenarios and following how the components interact.

Table 2 Architectural components and scenarios.

Green shade indicates the presence of an architectural component in each scenario.

Architecture components	PaN scenario 1: open data as input for a new experiment	PaN scenario 2: using a PaN analysis workflow	PaN scenario 3: EOSC researcher looking for PaN data
Facility endpoints to PaN search API (WP3)			
Facility endpoints to harvesters using OAI-PMH (WP3)			
Facility open data catalogue in EOSC (WP3)			
Data analysis service in EOSC (WP4)			
PaN analysis workflow (WP4)			
PaN training catalogue (WP5)			

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4.1. PaN scenario 1: PaN researcher looking for open data as input for a new experiment

Table 3 PaN scenario 1 walkthrough

Step	Scenario description	Implementation
1	The researcher is working at a university and is a registered user at one of the PaN facilities in Europe which gives him/her access to the compute resources	The researcher knows and can access PaN services, either the PaN open data portal or a facility data catalogue .
2	She is looking for published, non-embargoed data to fine-tune the initial parameters of her reflectometry model. She queries for all open data in the reflectometry domain.	The data portal offers both free-text and faceted search . It uses the PaN federated search service and forwards the query to each of the facilities endpoints. A filter is applied on the technique to return only reflectometry-related datasets. Results that each facility returns are merged and ranked by the PaN search service.
3	She narrows down the results to specific sample characteristics.	A new query is sent with an additional filter on parameters . Each facility provides a score and ranking is done with the result set from all RI's by the PaN search service.
4	She browses through the results, checking the metadata to see the relevant datasets and identifies a relevant dataset for further investigation at a particular facility.	The data portal displays additional metadata and links to related objects resolving PIDs.
5	She visualises the selected datasets and runs a well-established workflow on the data. She applies for beamtime to conduct a new experiment and validate her model with experimental data.	The data portal forwards her to the data analysis service of the facility hosting the dataset where she can access and analyse the data. OR the user is forwarded to the landing page of the data where it can be downloaded.

Fig. 10 Scenario 1 interaction between architectural components

4.2. PaN scenario 2: PaN researcher reusing one of the reference PaN analysis workflows

Table 4 PaN scenario 2 walkthrough

	Scenario description	Implementation
1	The researcher works at a university or a research institute and is looking for a THz spectroscopy analysis workflow.	The researcher browses and accesses the PaN training catalogue and learns how to do an analysis workflow.
2	She finds an existing analysis workflow and wants to validate it. She reproduces the analysis workflow using EOSC resources.	She can check if the results are the same as expected. She can access EOSC marketplace (UmbrellaID) and: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - finds a service and - downloads the Jupyter notebook (GitHub) - runs the analysis workflow, which is based on some reference datasets
3	She verifies the results and analyses new datasets with the selected workflow.	She goes to the EOSC marketplace to find a new data repository from HZDR, which will allow her to access new datasets from the data catalogue. A data transfer service is available from EOSC which allows the transfer of the data to the Jupyter notebooks.

Fig. 11 Scenario 2, interaction between architectural components

4.3. PaN scenario 3: Lecturer doing a thematic search that includes PaN data

Table 5 PaN scenario 3 walkthrough

	Scenario description	Implementation
1	A facility wants to make datasets available to the wider community in EOSC.	The facility implements the OAI-PMH interface and notifies EOSC for datasets harvesting and describes datasets with the required metadata (DataCite, DC).
2	EOSC harvests the datasets from the facilities.	B2FIND and OpenAire harvest the datasets exposed at facilities via the OAI-PMH interface .
3	A lecturer is teaching students solid state physics and wants to add new properties of perovskite materials for energy efficient solar cells as a new topic in her lecture notes.	The lecturer goes to the EOSC marketplace and searches for data catalogue portals and selects OpenAire explorer to search for perovskite materials and related fields.
4	The lecturer identifies 7 out of 10 data sets in the search results and finds two datasets of interests to update her notes.	The lecturer follows the DOI of the datasets which will take her to the respective landing page. She studies the information presented in the landing pages and identifies three datasets for download.

Fig. 12 Scenario 3 interaction between architectural components

5. Conclusion & Outlook

This deliverable describes the technical architecture of the ExPaNDS project on how to interface and federate current and possibly future services, locally provided by national PaN infrastructures, to a high-level scientific service, accessible via state of the art cloud interfaces. In consequence, this enables ExPaNDS to enrich the EOSC marketplace with specific, high profile PaN offerings.

The PaN data and services are exploited by a diverse and multidisciplinary set of users from almost all branches of the natural sciences and medicine ranging from physics, chemistry, biology, environmental sciences, materials engineering, cultural heritage, etc.. Satisfying the needs and requirements of the PaN community to provide FAIR data and Open Science is a complex endeavour. ExPaNDS has canalised the efforts from the National RI's in order to harmonise architectural approaches.

ExPaNDS architecture is not a single one-size-fits-all solution for all the NRIs, but rather it builds on architectural components and standardised API's that allow for multiple deployments and integrations according to the needs of the target discipline. In these efforts, ExPaNDS has identified commonalities among tools provided by project partners in their own facilities and has integrated common interfaces to abstract those services as they become available. This involves, but is not limited to, catalogues like ICAT and SciCat, access to cloud resources via Jupyter Notebooks or to HPC resources by means of remote desktops.

Defining standards and best practices on handling of data and on the composition of metadata is therefore a priority to make ExPaNDS data complying with FAIR principles. Similarly important for FAIRness is to work towards interoperability of Data Analysis platforms amongst project partners in ExPaNDS and PaNOSC, to guarantee future reproducibility of scientific results. In addition, a training and e-learning platform supports potential users in getting to know and applying the services and serves as a central information point.

Validation of the architecture is a constant stream throughout the project which is realised via the implementation of the real-life use cases, where verification, tests, and availability of the results and exploitation via the wider community in EOSC provide a continuous feedback channel and path for evolution.

The work and evolution of the architecture during the ExPaNDS project establishes strong foundations for its integration into the EOSC. Further developments and fine-tuning of its components will continue beyond ExPaNDS in the years to come.

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